

THE LINGERING EFFECTS OF PANDEMIC: THE JOURNEY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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The Lingering Effects of Pandemic: The Journey of English Language Teachers

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Abstract

This study aimed to discover the experiences, challenges encountered and gained insights of English language teachers with the lingering effects of pandemic in all elementary schools in District VI – Schools Division of Cotabato City. It employed qualitative research design using the semi-structured Key Informant Interview (KII) guide questions as gathering information. There has been no research highlighting the experiences of elementary English teachers upon the return of in-person classes. The findings revealed participants' experiences on the lingering effects of pandemic were adapting to changes in teaching-learning, basic skills development, impact on learning progress and development, technology and connectivity insufficiency and emotional toll and reflections on teaching effectiveness. Thus, with the learning of pupils were learning loss and academic gaps, impact on basic skills and comprehension, emotional response and bridging learning gaps and providing support. The challenges encountered were addressing learning loss and mental health, struggles in vocabulary comprehension, difficulty in teaching English and difficulty in adjusting to new learning environment. The interventions made were adaptability and flexibility in teaching methods, collaboration and community engagement, adapting teaching strategies, innovative teaching approaches, focus on student well-being, and continuous learning improvement. Lastly, gained insights were valuing the essence of resiliency with adaptability, flexibility and dedication, collaboration with innovation and support, continuous learning and professional growth, student-centered approach and well-being and human interactive connection with empathy. The findings have implications for educational policymakers, administrators and partners in other fields to intensify programs related in addressing the lingering effects of pandemic educationally and economically.

Keywords: *lingering effects, post COVID-19, English, Language teaching, experiences*

Introduction

The pandemic greatly influenced language teaching and learning among non-native English-speaking countries. It has side effects, especially in the scope of education and English as foreign language (EFL) teaching (Tümen-Akyıldız, Çelik & Ahmed, 2021). Relatively, as for English language teaching, Ahn and Chi (2023) from the University of Wisconsin-Madison discovered in their research study that language teachers have mixed feelings upon returning to face-to-face classes, unexpected challenges and adjustment techniques from the pandemic era.

The new normal education paved the way to discover new approaches for learning continuity. In an article, "COVID-19 and Education: The Lingering Effects of Unfinished Learning," the cumulative effects of the pandemic could have a long-term impact on an entire generation of students. Education achievement and attainment are linked not only to higher earnings but also to better health, reduced incarceration rates, and greater political participation (Dorn, Hancock, Sarakatsannis, Viruleg, 2021). Tümen-Akyıldız, Çelik & Ahmed (2021) cited that students and teachers experienced several difficulties during the pandemic.

It's been a while since the re-opening and implementation of full face-to-face classes in Philippines last August 2022. However, in a recent study conducted by World Bank, the Philippines was still among eight nations that registered a learning poverty rate higher than two-thirds, or 67 percent, despite the return of in-person classes in schools last November 2022 (Domingo, 2023).

Prior to re-opening of face-to-face classes, the curriculum, subject learning areas to be taught and learned and medium of instruction to be used were the same. According to a new World Bank (2021) report, Loud and Clear: Effective Language of Instruction Policies for Learning, effective language of instruction (LoI) policies are central to reducing Learning Poverty and improving other learning outcomes, equity, and inclusion. Consequently, according to website QQ English (2022), learning English in the Philippines is an essential part of its education system. It is a tool for learning and a medium of communication.

The Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao region is one of the contributors on the country's learning poverty. This is aligned with the Senate Hearing of Committee of Education held last August 23, 2023. Based on the press release posted on the official website of Senate of the Philippines, in a Senate hearing on the preparedness of basic education schools, Senator Gatchalian pointed to the low participation rates in BARMM, which are also lower than the nationwide averages (Senate of the Philippines, 2023).

Apparently, given the learning poverty situation in the country even after the re-opening of classes and low participation rate in BARMM region, thus, there is a need to discover and navigate the significant experiences of English language teachers in basic education on the lingering effects of pandemic after a school year of in-person classes. There has been no research highlighting the journey of elementary English language teachers upon the return of in-person classes. The study was conducted to explore the experiences, problems or challenges encountered and gained insights of elementary English language teachers with the lingering effects of pandemic as prevalent and continuous after returning to school in post-pandemic context, specifically in Schools Division of

Cotabato City.

Research Questions

This study aimed to discover the experiences of English language teachers with the lingering effects of pandemic in all elementary schools in District VI - Schools in Cotabato City Division. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic?
2. How do the English language teachers cope with the challenges and problems encountered?
3. What are the learning insights of English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed qualitative research design using the narrative research as approach method for “real world measures” (Hackett et.al., 2016) to understand the journey of English language teachers on their experiences on the lingering effects of pandemic upon the return of in-person classes.

Narrative research focuses on understanding and analyzing the stories and personal narratives shared by individuals. Researchers examine the structure, content, and context of these narratives to gain insights into how individuals construct meaning and make sense of their experiences (Jain, 2023).

Participants

The participants of the study were randomly selected elementary English language teachers in District VI of Cotabato City Division. They are teachers who teach English subject regardless of their bachelor's degree either elementary education or secondary education graduate.

The participants have been teaching English subject for at least two years and they have been in service for at least one year. They are also handling other assigned task as coordinator of different programs and projects in school where they teach.

Instrument

Key Informant Interview (KII) Guide Questions utilized as research instrument in this study. It was constructed by the researcher and validated by experts. The researcher received Certificate of Eligibility after the validation of the KII from the Dean's Office.

The KII Guide Questions were composed of semi-structured interviews. This was composed of three questions that dealt on experiences, challenges and insights of participants with the lingering effects of pandemic. The researcher prepared and used recording device, paper notes and pencil during the conduct of the interview.

Procedure

In gathering the data, the researcher asked permission from the office of Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study. This was followed by asking permission and courtesy to the concerned School Principals of all elementary schools in District VI. After the approval of all school administrators, the invitation letter was sent to selected English language teachers for an interview. The availability of the participants was considered to schedule the interview. The researcher explained sensibly the purpose of the interview and the importance of their participation in the conduct of the study. The letter of consent has given to participants on the conduct of interview.

Data Analysis

This study used qualitative analysis of data, which required thematic coding analysis. As cited by Nowell et. al (2017) on their article, Creswell (2014) described thematic analysis as a systematic process for coding data in which specific statements are analyzed and categorized into themes that represent the phenomenon of interest. According to Elliot (2018), coding is an almost universal process in qualitative research; it is a fundamental aspect of the analytical process and the ways in which researchers break down their data to make something new.” The need for coding is simple: “Text data are dense data, and it takes a long time to go through them and make sense of them” (Creswell, 2015, p. 152).

The researcher had read, re-read and proofread the recorded and transcribed interview recording to affluence the understanding of the data. The transcribed data was translated in English when the participants responded in Filipino or vernacular language and it will be analyzed, organized and encoded by the researcher.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations in qualitative research are pivotal to ensure the dignity, privacy and well-being of participants. Adhering to the ethical principles helps ensure the integrity, validity and trustworthiness of a qualitative research. This study was subjected for review of Ethics committee of the institution.

The researcher carefully considered the necessary ethical standards and considerations that were observed and followed all throughout the conduct of study. Furthermore, the researcher safeguarded the collection of informed consent, protected the confidentiality of the data, averted any unpredictable incidents and ensured participants have the right to withdraw at any time. Additionally, the researcher strived for honesty, transparency and integrity throughout the research process, including data collection, analysis and reporting.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and describes the results and corresponding analysis of the data gathered from the interview. The different themes emerged and illustrated the participant's answer to the research questions. The transcribed responses of the participants were compiled, sorted, classified and then interpreted by the researcher. This study used the Creswell (2013) thematic analysis in the presentation of data. This method is highly recommended in studying the journey in terms of experiences, challenges or problems encountered and learning insights of English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic.

The Experiences of the English Language Teachers on the Lingering Effects of Pandemic.

The English-language teacher participants were asked to share their experiences on the lingering effects of pandemic as prevalent and continuous after a school year of re-opening and implementation of in-person classes. For the experiences of the English language teachers, the emerging themes were categorized based on related experiences in teaching of language teachers and learning of pupils after pandemic. Thematic analysis of their responses on experiences led to the formation of five themes for teaching and four themes on learning respectively. Undeniably, the emerging themes were the long-term impact of pandemic to educational system basically, in teaching-learning processes.

Table 1.1. *The Experiences of the English Language Teachers on the Lingering Effects of Pandemic.*

Themes	Selected Quotations
Adapting to Changes in Teaching-Learning Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapting to online teaching, technology disparities, testing schedule disruptions. Complete shift in all aspects related to the teaching-learning process... Negative changes, particularly in public schools. Shift from face-to-face to remote and distance learning... Concerns about long-term impact on education and well-being. Transition to online teaching, challenges with internet connectivity... Emotional toll on teachers and learners.
Basic Skills Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges in teaching basic reading and writing skills... Inability of learners to sound letters, understand words, and write sentences. Poor reading skills, comprehension, and writing... Addressing reading difficulties and translating lessons for better understanding.
Impact on Learning Progress and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact on children's education, forgetting previously learned concepts... Short attention span and memory retention issues. Blended learning initially beneficial but led to low reading progress. Multiple factors affecting learning outcomes. Struggles in teaching English subject online or through modular learning... Limited acquisition of competencies during the pandemic.
Technology and Connectivity Insufficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges with internet connectivity leading to disruptions in online classes... Need for maintaining interaction with learners. Children's immersion in gadgets affecting learning habits... Difficulties in removing pandemic habits and distractions.
Emotional Toll and Reflections on Teaching Effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feelings of sadness and frustration over students' forgotten knowledge... Reflections on teaching effectiveness and personal shortcomings." Struggles in adapting to teaching English effectively...Doubts about teaching effectiveness amidst learning challenges.

Theme 1. Adapting to Changes in Teaching-Learning Process

The English language teacher-participants shared the same sentiments on the adaptation on the shift of teaching-learning delivery mode from remote and distance learning thru online or modular learning with many factors and challenges to be considered to implement the aforementioned mode of teaching-learning delivery especially in the kind of community environment they have where internet connectivity considered as a problem. Based on the participants' responses, the shift of delivery of teaching and learning English language is hard and ineffective somehow for both teachers and learners. Given the ineffective impact of remote learning during and after pandemic, it caused another sense of hardship for teachers upon the return of in-person classes.

Participant 1 and Participant 7 have related sentiments on the difficulty of teaching and learning English during and after pandemic:

"English language teachers have faced challenges like adapting to online teaching, addressing technology disparities among students, coping with disruptions to testing schedules, and adjusting curricula due to pandemic-related learning loss. As of today, we are still using the MELCS Based for different subjects," shared by Participant One.

Participant 7 shared, *“English language teachers have faced numerous challenge due to the lingering effects of pandemic. First, the transition to online teaching which required learning new technologies creating engaging digital materials. Second, teachers and pupils have faced challenges with internet connectivity leading to disruptions in online classes.”*

As an English language teacher, all these claims are true especially for the last miles school in Cotabato City Division. This is also affirmed by Moorhouse et al. (2021) that the language teachers and learners were not excuse at all as what revealed on their study that the global pandemic caused by the COVID-19 virus has had a disruptive and profound impact on English-language teaching. Most of the students had difficulty complying with the learning activities and requirements due to limited or no internet connectivity (Dayagbil et al., 2021).

Furthermore, both Participant Six, Seven and Eight were concerned to the impact of pandemic to the well-being of teachers and pupils emotionally and educationally. The following were the statements of the participants:

“Many teachers express concern about the long-term impact of the pandemic on the education and well-being of their students... The pandemic also has taken a toll on the emotional well-being of both teachers and learners... The pandemic really has a big impact in children’s education.”

Theme 2. Basic Skills Development

Based on the transcribed responses, basic skills development such as reading and writing were prioritized by the language teachers upon the return of in-person classes. This was response to the mandate from DepEd Central Office and MBHTE Regional Office on addressing learning loss and gaps due to the inability of learners in mastering the basic skills of learning. As mentioned in DepEd Order No. 34, series of 2022, the provision and development of holistic learning of learners were anchored to Basic Education Development Plan (BEDP) 2030 and department’s Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan from central to regional offices which were adopted and contextualized from RAPID Framework of UNICEF, UNESCO & World Bank (2022).

As mentioned, the participants experienced the challenges among learner’s performance in basic skills. Consequently, the language teachers were struggling as well in teaching basic reading and writing skills because of the inability of learners to sound letter, understand words and write sentences. One of the participants was struggling to get the full attention of the learners during class.

Participant Three expressed, *“Most of the learners are having a hard time in reading and in writing. They do not know the sounds of the letters in the alphabet or if they do, the next problem is if they do understand the meaning of the word they have just read... They lack the fundamental skills and knowledge which makes it harder to teach them lessons which are more complex.”*

Same sentiments with participant Five, *“The distance learning made the English language more distant to the learners. They struggle in reading and struggle more in comprehension. They cannot communicate using the language.”* As revealed by participant Five, translating the lesson to Filipino language makes the lesson understandable for learners.

Participant Six, together with participant Eight, Nine and Ten mentioned the lack of basic skills of learners. Addressing the problem were prioritized as mandated by higher-up official with policy and guidelines to be followed. Relatively, this experience of teachers on basic skills development were observed and addressed specifically to foundational grade learners in elementary level.

Theme 3. Impact on Learning Progress and Development

As the in-person classes have returned, evidently lingering impact of pandemic on learning progress and development have been observed and considered as notion in learning English language. Some of the participants mentioned that learners have short-term memory that lead them to be forgetful of the learned skills and concept being taught to them.

As one of the statements mentioned by Participant 8, *“It’s like you’re starting again to teach kindergarten because they’ve forgotten everything you’ve taught. Even their names, they forgot to write the correct stroke.”* This statement reflected on the findings of the study of Baltazar et al. (2023) that one of the challenges faced by teachers is the pandemic impact on students’ attitudes and learning.

As stated by Participant 9, *“At first, I am happy, because blended learning gives us, the teachers, extra time to accomplish our reports in our most convenient time... But as time goes by, this blended learning approach, specifically the modular learning modality, could give us a very low reading progress. So, there are different factors to that problem.”* This means that at some point, the pandemic gave some advantages and disadvantages in all aspects and race of life. According to the findings of the study of Emran et al. (2023), COVID-19 lockdown had positive implications for individuals and society, leading to increased health consciousness, improved family relationships, and constructive social attitudes. Moreover, the restrictions on access to natural tourist destinations and parks during the lockdown contributed to positive changes in biodiversity (Emran et al., 2023).

Hence, on the study of Dhole et al. (2021), they gave emphasis on the advantage and disadvantage of COVID-19 in academic. Accordingly, the mass effect of COVID -19 can be observed in all the sectors but more poorly affected to the economic and educational sector. In the education system, a great change of delivering classes from traditional mode to modern, i.e., online education though there are advantages and disadvantages of its but in the present era this is the most needful requirement of the world (Dhole et al., 2021). Noticeably, they have suggesting that the education system around the world should adapt to the development of technological

approach of teaching-learning setting for unpredictable circumstances in future.

Theme 4. Technology and Connectivity Insufficiency

Since the locale of the study in District VI were quite rural-type of environment, sustainability and availability of technological materials and internet connection are big factors can be considered why the online and modular distance learning were ineffective. In result, participants shared same sentiments during the conduct of interview. Participant One, Two and Seven shares about the addressing the technology and internet disparities and unavailability that leads to disruption of online class and task. This scenario was observed and experienced as well in District VI-Cotabato City Division. Given the fact as well that many of the students could not afford to access and provide technological tools on their ways of mean since pandemic left the home to be lockdown and many livelihoods were affected and had some delays.

These claims were evident in the report of Janssen (2022) on *“How COVID-19 Exposed Challenges for Technology in Education.”* It’s stated in the report that 800 million of learners from out of 1.6 billion in 194 countries around the world don’t have access to household computer, 700 million students don’t even have internet access at home and lastly, about 56 million students live in location are not served by mobile networks.

On the other hand, though there were few areas in research locale that ensured internet connectivity during pandemic, the problem arise were the learning focus and attention of pupils were affected. As shared by Participant Eight, the learners were immersed with gadgets that affect their learning habits and these gadgets resulted to lingering effect on difficulties in removing pandemic habits and distractions in re-opening of in-person classes.

Theme 5. Emotional Toll and Reflections on Teaching Effectiveness

The teachers’ preparedness and effectiveness (Baltazar et al., 2023) were one of the themes emerged in the study *“Navigating Communication Challenges in the Post-Pandemic Era: Perspectives from Teachers in a Philippine Higher Education Institution”*. Several of the participants shared that the lingering effects of the pandemic as for their experience were most likely involved the emotional well-being that affects their self-esteem and confidence as a language teacher. Some of them questioning their effectivity and efficiency as a teacher.

Participant Four, Five, Seven, Eight and Ten showed and shared emphasis on hardship or difficulty on teaching English language after pandemic that caused them to reflect on their effectivity and efficiency in teaching. Some of them were sad and struggled a lot during pandemic and after pandemic. With this, I can say that the emotional well-being of English language teachers was affected with the learning performance and situation of their learners.

This theme affirmed the study of Anero and Tamayo (2023), one of the findings on the experiences of the teachers was the challenging emotional experiences and one of the coping mechanisms was collaborative support and professional development.

Thus, while feeling this dilemma, based on experiences as English language teacher, continuous professional development and benchmarking of teaching strategies became the interventions for not to be carried away with the emotional turbulence during teaching & learning process. It is affirmed in the findings of Ahn and Chi (2023) on their study which revealed that while the language teachers embracing the mixed emotions upon the return of in-person classes, addressing unexpected challenges and adjusting teaching techniques, the teachers viewed their experiences as another learning opportunities that would immensely help them grow as professionals.

The Experiences on Learning of Pupils after Pandemic.

The English-language teacher participants were asked to share their experiences on the lingering effects of pandemic as prevalent and continuous on the learning of pupils after pandemic. Thematic analysis of their responses led to the formation of four themes. Undeniably, the emerging themes were the impact of pandemic to the learning habits of pupils as experience by the language teachers in in-person classes.

Table 1.2. *The experiences on learning of pupils after pandemic*

Themes	Selected Quotations
Learning Loss and Academic Gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many students faced challenges in catching up on missed learning... Frustration and anxiety among pupils at the beginning of school year. Difficulty in reading, writing, comprehension, and vocabulary development... Widening achievement gaps observed. Significant learning loss and academic gaps among learners... Social- emotional needs including anxiety, disconnection, and uncertainty.
Impact on Basic Skills and Comprehension	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learners lack basic knowledge and skills... Difficulty in maintaining attention and participation during discussions. Inability to sound English alphabet letters affecting daily teaching objectives... Upsetting results affecting teaching and learning outcomes.
Emotional Response and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Excitement among learners to return to school... Need to address learning gaps and

Adjustment to Returning to School	<p>struggles immediately.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hesitancy and lack of confidence in speaking English... Struggle in reading impacting participation in lessons.
Efforts to Bridge Learning Gaps and Provide Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower level of learning compared to face-to-face classes... Efforts to engage students and address learning disparities. • Challenges with oral communication and achievement gaps... Efforts to address learning difficulties and gaps in English subject.

Theme 1. Learning Loss and Academic Gaps

Learning loss and academic gaps can be referred to discrepancy between knowledge and skills that students should have acquired and mastered at a particular grade level or stage of education. Thus, the learning loss and academic gaps were experienced even before pandemic. But the crisis on pandemic made it worse than before.

These situations were due to various factors, such as extended breaks from traditional learning environments, inadequate access to resources, or disparities in learning opportunities and some other factors.

All around the world, learning losses were observed across all grade levels. When it came to standardized tests, declines were seen in proficiency rates or percentile scores, especially in math and reading (Torres, 2024).

As elaborated in a study, school disruptions and learning losses have a wide range of economic and social effects. Lower levels of learning due to fewer years of effective schooling translates into deficient development of cognitive skills (measured by scores in standardized tests). In turn, lower cognitive skills will likely reduce the future earnings potential and labor-market opportunities of the students affected. All of this could eventually translate into lower economic productivity for the nation as a whole (Pinto, 2023).

The participants shared their experiences on encountering and addressing the learning loss and academic gaps during and after pandemic. Participant Four shared that many students have faced challenges in catching up on missed learning.

Participant Six noted that based on the learning experience of the pupils after pandemic, there are some key problems faced by pupils in English subject such as difficulty in reading, poor reading comprehension, decline in developing of writing skills, reduced vocabulary development, challenges with oral communication which resulted the widening of academic achievement gaps.

Participant Seven and Eight collectively stated that they observed significantly the learning loss and gaps among their pupils. They observed the urgency to address the social-emotional problems such as feelings of anxiety, disconnection and uncertainty upon the return of in-person classes.

These feelings and observation on learning loss and academic gaps were validated in the study of Anero and Tamayo (2023) on the findings that the teachers were having students-centered focus approach since one of the emerging themes in the challenges as lingering effects of pandemic upon the return of in-person classes is the learning loss and academic challenges.

Theme 2. Impact on Basic Skills and Comprehension

Undeniably, as aforementioned, there's impact on the development of basic skills and comprehension on pupil's learning. In support to understand how basic skills and comprehension can be acquired and developed, we need to have an anatomy on the learning styles and habits of pupils before, during and after pandemic.

The learning styles are preferences of the child on how they can learn meaningfully. This is the ability of learner to acquire, decode, understand, restore and retrieve for utilization or application of basic knowledge or skills. Lorina (2018) mentioned that there are three different learning styles. These include Visual Learners- they see to learn, Auditory Learners - they hear to learn and Kinesthetic Learners - they move to learn.

Relatively, participant Three shared that learners lack basic knowledge and skills resulted in difficulty in maintaining attention and participation during discussions. As for experience, the teacher should adjust the teaching strategies and activities that best suit the pupils' learning style after pandemic.

Another upsetting scenario shared by participant Nine was the inability of the language learners to produce sound of English alphabet letters. Participant Nine said during interview, *"After assessing their learning ability using the CRLA tool, the result shows that some of my pupils cannot sound the letters of the English Alphabet. So, this result really bothers me because it is affecting my daily teaching and learning objectives."*

Hence, this scenario on impact on basic skills and comprehension were present even before of pandemic. The claims of the participant confirmed more the report findings of UNICEF and other concerned agencies before and during pandemic. UNICEF (2022) stated in report that prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, an estimated 50 million primary school-age children in the East Asia and Pacific region were failing to learn basic foundational skills in core subjects, such as language, mathematics and science (UNESCO, 2017b). Up to 80 per cent of children in some countries fail to master foundational reading, writing and mathematics skills by the end of primary school (UNICEF & SEAMEO, 2020).

Theme 3. Emotional Response and Adjustment to Returning to School

There are different emotions emerged during the return of classes after pandemic. The re-opening and implementation of in-person class brought excitement and joy learners. Hence, these feelings were mixed up with anxiousness. Relatively, classroom anxiety uniformly increased in the post lockdown period due to preventive policies adhered when schools reopened, such as wearing masks, sanitizing hands, and maintaining social distancing (Rashid, 2022).

Above statements were evident in the experiences of teachers they have shared upon the opening and return of in-person classes. During the interview, participant Eight shared, *“For almost a year hanging around the house and not being able to go out, you can see in their faces how excited they are. From bags, notebooks, uniforms and school supplies, all new and complete. Their joy overflowed when they knew that they could go back to school already. And much happier to meet if who would be their teacher and classmates.”*

Above statements must be applied prior to the official opening of classes. As for the situation in English class, participant Ten shared that using the mother tongue ease comprehension among pupils. The participant said, *“I find them struggling to understand the lesson especially when I’m using English language. So most of the time I’m using their mother tongue... The pupils were very hesitant to participate because they were not confident to speak in English language and even struggling to read.”*

In a website article written by Spaulding (2023), it posted that when the classes back in classrooms, teachers faced the challenge of making up for lost learning and filling in all students' academic gaps, while dealing with post-COVID physical, mental, social, and emotional difficulties.

Theme 4. Efforts to Bridge Learning Gaps and Provide Support

Since the pandemic, different agencies, non-government organizations, education partners and stakeholders worked hand in hand to address the continuous impact of pandemic to economy and to education. Enable to bridge the learning gaps, some of the teacher-participants like participant One, Five & Ten shared that utilization of mother tongue language helps to instill understanding among pupil and lowering the standard in teaching methodologies and content of the lesson for easier grasp of the lesson. With these efforts, learners were engaged in addressing learning disparities.

Participant Five, Six and Seven collectively shared during the interview that challenges with oral communication and achievement (learning) gaps in English language class, providing academic support, lowering the standards if necessary and establishing social-emotional guidance are needed for the learners to thrive in class.

However, aside from this effort, various program for learning recovery and interventions were initiated as well to help reduce the impact of pandemic in learning loss and gaps. As mentioned in the report, learning recovery and intervention were intensified during and after pandemic. As stated by Gianini, Jenkins, Saavedra and Schleicher (2022), *“...While countries have made some progress in implementing measures that address learning recovery, we must upsurge our efforts to mitigate the pandemic's impact on children's learning and well-being.”*

English language teachers challenges and problems encountered.

The English-language teacher participants were asked to elaborate how they cope up with the challenges or problems they have encountered on the lingering effects of pandemic upon re-opening of in-person classes. Thematic analysis of their responses led to the formation of four themes. Undeniably, the emerging themes were the collective responses of how they address the challenges or problems along the way on the conduct of in-person classes.

Table 2.1. English language teachers challenges and problems encountered.

Theme	Selected Quotations
Addressing Learning Loss and Mental Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilizing interactive lessons and providing additional support... addressing learning losses and supporting student's mental health and well-being. Prioritizing professional development and self-care... adapting to changing circumstances and maintaining well-being.
Struggles in Vocabulary Comprehension	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges in building vocabulary and comprehension... Adjusting teaching methods to accommodate comprehension difficulties. Struggles in reading, comprehension, and communication... Translating lessons to the first language for better understanding.
Challenges in Teaching English Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty in teaching English to young learners in rural areas... Academic freeze affecting learning English. Challenges in teaching English language to full refresher or non- readers... Learning loss impact on pupils. Struggles with distance learning and modules for teaching English... Disparities in learning outcomes.
Challenges in Adjusting to New Learning Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing a routine in a classroom setting after the pandemic has become a challenge... Children's attention span became shorter, especially in learning English. Struggles in communication and comprehension... Consuming time to revisit basic lessons

to aid understanding.

- Struggling to understand lessons, especially in English... Lowering teaching standards to accommodate struggling learners.
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Theme 1. Addressing Learning Loss and Mental Health

Maba, Widiastuti, Mantra, Suartama and Sukanadi (2023) find out on their study that there was a learning loss during and after the COVID-19 pandemic and had an impact on students' psychological conditions in learning. As suggested, the study's result implies that teachers must consider the conditions of student learning loss and always try to find the right solution to improve students' abilities to reduce the learning loss.

Based on the transcribed responses of language teachers, participant One, Seven and Nine mutually shared that some of coping mechanism they have done involves utilization of interactive lessons, sharing additional support either technical or ideals, prioritizing and acquiring professional development and adhering to self-care with mental health and maintaining the well-being of oneself both teachers and learners.

Participant One shared, *“English language teachers cope with challenges by utilizing and creating an interactive lesson, providing additional support to students struggling in their lesson, specifically reading and fostering a sense of community connection.”*

Participant Seven expressed, *“Professional Development plays vital role because it allows us to enhance our skills, stay updated on best practices and learn new teaching strategies to address challenges... Being adaptable and flexible in response to changing circumstances “we need also to prioritize self-care to maintain well-being and effectiveness in the classroom.”*

Participant Nine added, *“As an English language teacher, in order to cope up with these challenges, I manage my time flexible... I always find and use any interventions that could help my learners and I related to my teaching career.”*

Based on my experiences as an English teacher and Reading Coordinator in our school, upon the re-opening of in-person classes, all of the teachers were required to have Psychosocial and First-Aid Training.

The aforementioned training was one of the proposed programs of UNESCO, UNICEF & World Bank under the Mission: Recovery Education 2021 which has three priorities: a.) All children and young people are back in school and receive the tailored services needed to meet their learning, health, psychosocial well-being, and other needs, b.) Students receive effective remedial learning to help recover learning losses and c.) All teachers are prepared and supported to address learning losses among their students and to incorporate digital technology into their teaching (Mott MacDonald International Development, 2022).

The Psychosocial and First-Aid Training really helped in conditioning one's mental health. Collaborative effort among teachers, parents and other stakeholders thrived to make things after pandemic easier to absorb and process. Though there are upsetting moment especially with the situation on learning loss and gaps among pupils, resiliency and hopefulness made positivity with all those problems we have to deal with in school after the pandemic.

Theme 2. Struggles in Vocabulary and Comprehension

As shared by the language teachers from transcribed responses on their experiences on the learning of pupils, the learners were struggling to understand the lesson. Lack of vocabulary and poor comprehension lead to low performance of pupils in class especially in English. Participant Two and Six both admitted that their learners were lack of vocabulary and developing English vocabulary words among pupils have become problem in their class. On the other hand, participant Five and Six expressed that they were translating lessons to first language for better understanding of the lesson. This is the result of how many years of remote learning at home. Given the situation, the language teachers opt to assess the learning levels of their pupils and adjust teaching methods and approaches to accommodate comprehension difficulties.

Participant Two expressed, *“Because of the pandemic and the academic freeze, building up vocabulary in English words have become a problem in my class. The same as their comprehension. My pupils were very challenged in understanding sentences using English words. I cope with the challenges through knowing my pupils. By thinking on my pupil's situation, I have been able to adjust my teaching so the learning will be effect knowing to adjust is a good coping mechanism and very effective me.”*

Participant Five exclaimed, *“My last resort is to discuss (the lesson) into simplest language or translate to first language such as Filipino.”*

Participant Six shared, *“I have encountered several challenges which were prevalent in English language teaching and learning. First, poor reading skills of learners. This problem was worse global crisis during pandemic and even after pandemic. Second, the independent readers have poor reading comprehension and lack of vocabulary words. During teaching-learning process even after opening of class, I have to translate the words from English to Mother-Tongue language or Filipino to understand the lesson and to keep on track on the discussion.”*

The adaptability and flexibility in teaching such as translating English words to mother tongue language and adjusting the difficulty level of the lessons for better grasping of comprehension among learners were considered as instructional modification and flexibility.

Relatively, to affirm to this instructional modification in post-pandemic setting, it was revealed on the study of Eslit, Lector & Enad (2024), educators in School Division of Iligan City have portrayed resilience and adaptability by integrating educational technology, implementing flexible instructional approaches and embracing professional development.

Theme 3. Challenges in Teaching English Language

The language teachers have shared their challenges in teaching English language even after the pandemic. Evidently, the lingering effect even after the pandemic has long-term impact in teaching English especially to the elementary pupils. As shared by one of the teacher-participants, *“As an English Teacher teaching in Grade 3, one of the experiences that I could say an effect of the pandemic was teaching the language itself. It became more difficult for me to relate English to my pupils especially I have been teaching in a rural area. Far from the influence of internet, here, the children are very used to their mother tongue. The academic freeze due to pandemic became a challenge on learning English. At first, it was difficult, as the children were used in speaking their mother tongue, introducing English in a very young learners were a challenge,”* said by Participant Two.

The above statements of the participants affirmed to the study of Baltazar et al. (2023) concluded that there are five specific challenges that was faced by the teachers: (1) pandemic impact on students’ attitudes and learning, (2) language and communication barriers, (3) technological challenges in education, (4) lack of infrastructures building gaps in classroom environment and (5) teachers’ preparedness and effectiveness (Baltazar et al., 2023).

Several of the teacher participants felt emotional and questions their effectivity as teacher over the challenges they encountered in teaching English. Participant Eight sadly shared, *“The pandemic really has a big impact in children’s education... I feel like crying out of sadness... Sometimes, I just asked myself, “Am I still an effective teacher? Where did I fall short, what did I do wrong in teaching even though I did everything?”*

Some of them shared the same challenges such as poor reading skills of learners resulted to low reading performance and going back to basic lessons and widening of learning loss and gaps.

“During pandemic and until now, as an English teacher, I face and find it challenging to teach English language especially those learners categorized as full refresher or non-readers,” revealed by Participant Four.

“I thought of my pupils. I thought, how will my struggling learners cope with the lessons. Hearing how they stutter in reading, how they hardly answer comprehension questions. How will I help them? The problem wasn’t new, it’s been there before the COVID-19 but the pandemic made the problem bigger,” participant Five expressed.

Anero and Tamayo (2023) revealed and identified on their study the challenges encountered faced by teachers and schools during the full implementation of in-person classes. As stated, these challenges encompassed issues related to classroom infrastructure and facilities, learning gaps and academic challenges, behavioral issues and student discipline, safety and security, teacher workload and teaching loads, student engagement and parent involvement, gender-responsive policy and early pregnancy, professional development and learning materials (Anero & Tamayo, 2023).

As revealed by Ahn and Chi (2023), with pedagogical uncertainties, language teachers exercised agency by integrating technology into teaching, employing new teaching strategies, extending their roles to caregivers and community builders, and reflecting on future teaching practices.

Theme 4. Challenges in Adjusting to New Learning Environment

While adapting to changes in teaching-learning process, challenges along the way of adaptation will not be excluded. Teacher-Participant Two and Four specifically shared that establishing and adapting to routine in classroom setting after pandemic has become difficult since children’s attention span became shorter especially in learning English.

On the other hand, participant Five, Six, Nine and Ten both shared during the conduct of interview respectively that their learners were struggling to communicate and understand the lesson especially in English.

Basically, to aid the learners’ comprehension on the lesson, participant One, Five and Ten admitted that they’re lowering the teaching and learning standards for the struggling learners. They’re reviewing the basic lessons though it’s time consuming.

Furthermore, adjusting to a new learning environment after reopening classes can be challenging for learners. Here are few common difficulties they might face such as adapting to socialization, addressing the academic gaps, technological adaptation when there’s abrupt shift of learning delivery and routine disruption. Addressing these challenges may require a combination of support from teachers, peers, and families, as well as a flexible and understanding approach to accommodate individual needs during the transition period.

These challenges were witnessed by English Professor from Writluxe University, Takara M. Carter (2023), on her English class. She shared on her LinkedIn page that as schools around the world have reopened their classrooms after the Covid-19 pandemic, educators are facing new challenges in managing their classrooms. With the hybrid learning model and social distancing protocols in place, the traditional classroom dynamics have shifted, and educators must adapt to new academic trends and find ways to engage their students.

The interventions made by the teachers/school.

With the challenges and problems encountered during and after the pandemic, several interventions with innovations emerged inside and outside the school setting. Several of the language teachers shared what interventions were initiated either within school or adapted from other stakeholders. Thematic analysis of their responses led to formation of six themes.

Table 2.2. *The interventions made by the teachers/school*

Theme	Selected Quotations
Adaptability and Flexibility in Teaching Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English Language teachers gained insight into the importance of flexible teaching methods, the online, modular, or in-person learning environment. As a teacher, I need to be always flexible... I need to be resilient and have patience in dealing with challenges such as technical issues and asynchronous learning. To address the challenges... it is crucial to Integrate interactive and engaging learning activities... and utilize digital tool resources.
Collaboration and Community Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pandemic proved us that a glitch in the educative process will yield great problems... I believe these lingering effects of the pandemic needed our collaborative efforts to solve it little by little. We intensified our reading programs and remedial classes... The widespread adoption of technology during the pandemic has highlighted the importance of digital literacy skills for both teachers, parents, and learners. Teachers engage parents and community members in supporting students' learning both at school and at home.
Adapting Teaching Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing strategies suited to learners' diverse learning styles... Professional development, collaboration, flexibility, and adaptability. Challenges in motivating and teaching struggling readers... Adjusting teaching methods to engage students and address reading difficulties.
Innovative Teaching Approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The English Teachers in our school came up with a solution and made interventions.... engaging the pupils in more fun and collaborative activities. Teachers utilize technology-based instruction, such as video lessons and interactive activities, to enhance student engagement and comprehension." In order to address the learning losses of the learners, various activities and DepEd programs are being conducted... to enhance learning experiences.
Focus on Student Well-being	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pandemic has led me to profound realizations about the effects of crisis situations in education, prompting reflection, adaptation, and innovation in the pursuit of a resilient and equitable educational system. The situation made me realize that our role as teachers is even more important these days... technology and the internet could teach anyone so many things... but nothing beats learning from people like us who have real-life experiences. As a teacher, I must see to it that I possess what a teacher of Bangsamoro should have... so that I could provide a chance to develop, enhance, and make a change for the future of Bangsamoro learners.
Continuous Learning and Improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The important realization I conclude is that as a teacher, I need to be flexible and resilient in delivering quality education to my learners... teachers should be dynamic at all times. Since the learners have poor vocabulary, I see to it that they can learn at least 10 words with meaning and pictures every day... using technology-based instruction is very effective for my learners.

Theme 1. Adaptability and Flexibility in Teaching Methods

Several teacher-participants shared that to enable cope up with the challenges, there are interventions made either within teacher level, school level or within the department's level. These initiatives for solution to the problems and challenges should be adapted with flexibility. Some of the participants appreciated the importance of flexibility in teaching methods and deliveries either thru online, modular or in-person learning environment.

Participant Five elaborated, *"The problem became more complex that one solution might not answer everything thus teacher has to think about more ways to solve it. I have to take my fight to the next level. I double time for the struggling learners by giving them task that suitable to their level of understanding. I made sure that they continue reading and learning from school to their homes by giving them materials to practice on weekends. I made self-learning modules considering the contexts of my pupils. I reached out to those who are unable to get modules. I teach online for those who have access to the internet. I conduct study about supports of parents at home such as educational attainment of the parents."*

Participant Six shared the complexity in adapting technology integration in class, *"To address the challenges or problems I have encountered in my class, it is crucial to integrate interactive and engaging learning activities in English lesson since our learners experienced the learning loss and gap. With this, I have provided opportunities for meaningful language practice and I utilized digital*

tool resources.”

Participant Ten expressed during the interview, *“As a teacher, we should be flexible and resourceful enough to think of various strategies to be used.”*

As affirmation, Farrell (2021) concluded on his study that language teacher educators will need to reconsider how they prepare learner language teachers to develop their digital competence in order to better serve the needs of their students. I agree with this since it’s pivotal to consider the training on digital competence of the language educators to sustain the adaptability and flexibility in teaching and learning.

Theme 2. Collaboration and Community Engagement

Collaboration and engagement among stakeholders and education partners played pivotal role for learning continuity and acceleration amidst of pandemic and ways forward after pandemic. Several of the English language teacher-participants shared their collaboratives efforts made with co-teachers and parents, school initiatives and community engagement.

Participant Three mentioned during the interview, *“Stakeholders, especially the parents of the learners, have been tapped for help. Hoping that as the school and the community work together, learners will learn better.”*

Participant Six shared some of the projects they have worked out together with the PTA Officers, *“I have collaborated with PTA Officers in my class to purchase SMART TV to upgrade my instructional materials. I constantly communicating with my parents to follow-up and update the parents on the learning needs and improvement of their children. This is a big step to provide sustainability and necessary support.”*

I believed also that learning continuity would be impossible without the cooperation of all stakeholders especially on the part of parents and learners. It takes a lot of trust and resource especially with time and effort for the parents to let their children continue their learning despite anxiety and uncertainty they’ve experience during and after pandemic.

I believed as well that in times of crisis and recovery, the strong partnership of school to its stakeholders was one of the effective and efficient way to make deliverables in school thrived and sustained. As one of the coping mechanisms revealed by Anero and Tamayo (2023), the collaborative support and effective communication involvement of stakeholders are some of the interventions made by the teachers after the return of in-person classes.

Theme 3. Adapting Teaching Strategies

Teachers had to adapt, learn new technologies, and rise to many challenges facing them on a daily basis (Mahoney, 2023). Adaptability remarks as one of the survival traits of human race to conquer the pandemic during and after its devastating stage. Same goes with educational context, adaptability with new teaching approaches and methodologies were necessary to enable things work enormously.

As recommended by World Bank (2022) on the R.A.P.I.D. Framework, as third action to be made, prioritize teaching fundamentals means to conduct much-needed adjustment to better align curricula with pressing needs. As elaborated in the framework, countries should adjust teaching plans to prioritize teaching the fundamentals in the time they have available.

Several of the teacher participants shared that they cope up with the pandemic by adapting new teaching approaches and strategies with professional development training and flexibility and adjustment with time-on-task and collaboration with others and stakeholders thru mentoring or benchmarking.

Participant Four shared, *“In our school, just to cope with the challenges encountered, we made these following strategies: first, Professional Development – we have School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) every week and second, Collaboration with stakeholders and lastly, developing the flexibility and adaptability by addressing the problem immediately.”*

Participant Seven elaborated, *“Professional Development plays vital role because it allows us to enhance our skills, stay updated on best practices and learn new teaching strategies to address challenges. Collaborating with colleagues provide us with support system to share ideas and resources and being adaptable and flexible in response to changing circumstances.”*

Participant Nine shared, *“As an English language teacher, in order to cope up with these challenges, I manage my time flexibly... I always find and use any interventions that could help my learners and I related to my teaching career.”*

Participant Five mentioned how he adjusted his teaching approaches when the learners cannot grasp and understand the lesson, *“My last resort is to discuss into simplest language or translate to first language such as Filipino.”*

In a study concluded, it affirmed that the English teachers also made innovation and were very creative in designing learning by choosing the appropriate strategies, models, and media to support learning and gain students interest to improve their English skill. The selection of the appropriate learning media during the limited face to face learning is able to produce good output according to the needs and existing conditions (Wirawati, Laili & Nashir, 2022). It remarked as the language teachers adapted and adjusted to the new learning set-up brought about by the pandemic, new innovations were discovered for catering the needs of the learners across the globe.

Theme 4. Innovative Teaching Approaches

The learning loss during pandemic has many factors. Post-pandemic learning loss is related to digital disconnection between teachers and students (Aguaded et al., 2023). Relatively, the evolution of mode of teaching and learning delivery amidst of pandemic involved the socio-economic and technological needs among teachers, learners and parents. Relatively, to prove this, in Middle east countries, according to study of Khreisat (2022), there were many strategies in teaching English language during pandemic. Hence, there were three significant strategies emerged effectively for the language learners in Middle east such as collaborative learning (i.e., breakout classes, cloud-based collaboration), the second is flipped classroom, and the final is scaffolding (Khreisat, 2022).

Providing digital tool resources has become norm until the return of in-person classes. This initiative can be considered as innovational move for more effective and efficient delivery of teaching and learning process.

Both parents and teachers aimed to give and deliver quality education by upgrading the instructional materials in classroom. The participants shared during the interview of the innovative teaching approaches they initiated together with the support and guidance of the school administrators from central to division offices down to schools.

Participant One shared generally, *“In order to address the learning losses of the learners, various activities and DepEd programs is being conducted like the reading program, different interventions and strong implementation Instructional supervision.”*

Participant Two elaborated some of the detailed approaches made by English language teachers, *“The English Teachers in our school came up to a solution and made interventions to these problems by engaging the pupils to a more fun and collaborative activities. The school put a television on our covered court, and every morning, we let the pupils watch educational videos that are enticing to the pupils. We also have vocabulary check activities such as spelling and games every start of our lesson. We also develop their comprehension through simply introducing to them words and use the environment and the things they can see in teaching them.”*

Participant Six added, *“I have provided opportunities for meaningful language practice and I utilized digital tool resources.”*

Participant Ten emphasized the contribution of video lessons for the learners’ comprehension-aid, *“I also used video lesson for them especially let them watch short stories. For me, using technology-based instruction is very effective for my learners.”*

To reiterate the innovative ways made by teachers, as noted the English teachers also made innovation and were very creative in designing learning by choosing the appropriate strategies, models, and media to support learning and gain students interest to improve their English skill. The selection of the appropriate learning media during the limited face to face learning is able to produce good output according to the needs and existing conditions (Wirawati, Laili & Nashir, 2022).

The aforementioned findings of the study were true at all. Optimism in crisis opened new opportunities to learn and innovate. Based on my experience in our school, I initiated the *“KAHONRUNUNGAN: A Reading Program Initiative Project,”* which have started from pandemic and have continued upon the return of in-person classes.

Theme 5. Focus on Student Well-Being

Students’ social-emotional well-being matters and is connected to their achievement in school. There are two key components of well-being that we’ll define and discuss: emotions and social support (Moulton, 2024). Alongside with the coping mechanism and intervention, the psychological aspects of teachers’ clientele should be considered as well. It’s one of the major factors to consider for the effectivity and efficiency of meaningful learning to happen. Some of the teacher-participants shared the interventions they made in regards with psychological needs of learners especially on their mental health.

Participant One shared how the school address the mental health issue in their school, *“In terms of mental health, before the opening of the classes, the school conducted the so called psychological first-aid training for teachers so that they will equip with the skills needed for the learners.”*

One of the participants valued as well their importance as teachers in times of crisis when education needs to continue no matter what, *“The situation made me realize that our role as teachers is even more important these days. Technology and the internet could teach anyone so many things, but nothing beats learning from people like us who have real-life experiences.”*

I also believed that no one can place teacher who have both intelligent and emotional quotient at the same time. Only health and emergency situation can hinder the situation to impart knowledge and mold skills of our learners.

Theme 6. Continuous Learning and Improvement

Learning continuity and development was sustained accordingly to the responses of language teachers. It was revealed on the study of Eslit, Lector & Enad (2024), educators in School Division of Iligan City have portrayed resilience and adaptability by integrating educational technology, implementing flexible instructional approaches and embracing professional development. As shared by one of the participants, this effort was sustained with resiliency, adaptability and flexibility skills of learners and teachers. Challenges were addressed with research and intervention. Adjustments took place when one approach is least effective or not working, still learning is continuous and dynamic.

Participant Four shared about their utilization and sustainability of one intervention in reading which was effective for their school to continue. As shared by participant Four, “*Our school made an intervention so called, “Picture Ko, Basahin Mo” (My Picture, You Read) – an intervention aims to solve the problem in reading. This intervention applied by all teacher in our school where they focus their teaching in reading. We’re still using this intervention until now because it’s effective for us.*”

Based on my experience as School Reading Coordinator in our school, we sustained the projects and programs that works for our learners’ needs and context as well.

To tailored this, participant Ten shared, “*As a teacher, we should be flexible and resourceful enough to think of various strategies to be used. Since the learners have poor vocabulary, I see to it that they can learn at least 10 words with meaning and pictures every day... I also used video lesson for them especially let them watch short stories. For me, using technology-based instruction is very effective for my learners.*”

Participant Nine added that teachers are extending their time in school for the implementation of these interventions to fast track the improvement of learning since there are learning loss and gaps to reclaim and fill-in.

The learning insights of English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic.

The English language teacher-participants were asked to share their learning insights on the lingering effects of pandemic as prevalent and continuous on the learning of pupils after pandemic. The gained insights were focused on the take-aways, impact and realizations made by the participants. Thematic analysis of their responses led to the formation of five themes for the first identifying question which is the language teachers’ take-aways on the lingering effect of pandemic.

Table 3.1. *The learning insights (take-aways) of English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic.*

Theme	Selected Quotations
Resilience and Adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The lingering effects of the pandemic have provided insights into the importance of adaptability to any unexpected circumstances. I must be resilient and have patience in dealing with challenges such as technical issues and asynchronous learning. The pandemic has fostered the essence of solidarity and collaboration among us as we have come together to share resources, strategies, and support.
Importance of Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration among teachers, parents, community stakeholders, and education partners are pivotal for the continuation of education despite all odds that hampers the learning continuity. The pandemic proved us that a glitch in the educative process will yield great problems among our dear pupils thus education must continue. The widespread adoption of technology during the pandemic has highlighted the importance of digital literacy skills for both teachers, parents, and learners.
Student Well-being and Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addressing and prioritizing the well-being of both teachers and learners. Education must not be taken for granted... Being able to teach and learn in school and in classrooms faced-to-faced is far better. To cope with the less interested learners in schooling, I make sure that my instructional materials are updated and suited to their interests.
Continuous Learning and Improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Even after the pandemic, I felt the urged need to teach the language accurately. Little learning is good when it is continuous regardless of DepEd MELCS. Encountering the challenges and problems caused by the lingering effect of the pandemic in education have provided insights into... investing and uplifting the professional development of educators. As an English language teacher, I should learn, relearn, and unlearn some trends in teaching so that I can provide the best teaching methods and strategies for my pupils.
Reflection and Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English Language teachers gained insight into the importance of flexible teaching methods... Overall, the pandemic has prompted reflection on various aspects of society. With the lingering effects of the pandemic, it only showed us drastically how change and uncertainty remain as constants in the academe... however, education still remains as one of the most essential things one needs to thrive in life. Pandemic is just a challenge, it's up to you on how you face it... Just trust and have faith that all learners can read through your effort and parents' cooperation.

Theme 1. Resilience and Adaptability

The participants were asked to share their insights or take-aways on the lingering effects of pandemic. And one of the themes prevailed during the interview was the idea of resilience and adaptability. Resiliency and adaptability were interconnected with each other.

Several of the participants mentioned that resiliency and adaptability embodied them as modern-hero combatting the pandemic and its lingering effect. The majority of the participants shared during the interview on how such traits helped them to push teaching and

learning despite of anxiety and uncertainty during and after pandemic period.

Participants shared:

“The lingering effects of pandemic have provided several insights and take-aways. These are resilience and adaptability, digital transformation, health and well-being, economic impacts and environmental awareness,” participant One shared.

“With the lingering effects of the pandemic, it only showed us drastically how change and uncertainty remain as constants in the academe and in this world, we live in. Thus, as teachers, we must continue to adjust, to develop, to evolve, to adapt, and to improve ourselves so we can play our role in our society the best way possible,” participant Three expressed.

“As an English language teacher, I gained several insights on the lingering effects of pandemic. First, I as a teacher, I need to be always flexible in a sense that I can be adaptable whatever form of teaching or way of teaching I should deliver. Second, as a teacher, I must know what my learners need and I should focus on that need. Lastly, as a teacher, I need to be resilient and have patience in dealing with challenges such as technical issues and asynchronous learning. I need to be adaptive to unforeseen and unpredictable circumstances,” participant Four said.

“Encountering the challenges and problems caused by lingering effect of the pandemic in education have provided insights into the importance of adaptability to any unexpected circumstances, addressing and prioritizing the well-being of both teachers and learners, intensifying the collaboration among school and community stakeholders, promoting of personalized learning, investing and uplifting the professional development of educators, adapting the hybrid learning for flexibility and emergency situations and enhancing pupils involvement and participation on their responsibility as learners,” participant Six remarked.

“The take-aways that I have been learned from the pandemic have reshaped education in profound ways, renewed focus on adaptability, resilience, collaboration, flexible learning among learners and development of digital literacy skill,” participant Seven stated.

These insights were agreed similarly by Torres (2024) as noted on the introductory part of the website she authored, *“The pandemic taught us quite a few lessons when it comes to dealing with the unprecedented. In the educational sphere, COVID-19 presented us with a few challenges. It also left us with some significant changes, especially when it came to learning beyond the classroom and reaching students despite school closures.”* These learned traits and take-aways highlight the adaptability of humans in the core of unprecedented challenges and likely to have lasting impacts on how society functions in post-pandemic and future.

Theme 2. Importance of Collaboration

Collaboration is important to make teaching and learning more efficient and effective. Some of the participants mentioned that along with adaptability, collaboration or cooperation plays pivotal role to make learning continuous and accelerate to transformational education.

Participant One expressed, *“Overall, the pandemic has prompted reflection on various aspects of society, from how we work and learn how we prioritize health and well-being.”*

Participant Seven elaborated, *“It also underscored me the importance of flexibility in teaching and learning. The widespread adoption of technology during the pandemic has highlighted the importance of digital literacy skills for both teachers, parents and learners. The pandemic has fostered the essence of solidarity and collaboration among us as we have come together to share resources, strategies and support.”*

Participant Five noted the importance of parental and follow-up guidance from home to school and vice versa. The following statement was shared, *“The pandemic proved us that a glitch in the educative process will yield great problems among our dear pupils thus education must continue. Education must continue from school to home. That is after listening and learning to teachers at school, learners should be taught again by their parents at home. Parents should mind the welfare of their children by checking what they have learned at school and having it reviewed at home regularly. I believe these lingering effects of the pandemic needed our collaborative efforts to solve it little by little.”*

The above-mentioned statements confirmed and agreed to the statement of Reyes (2024) on her blog post that collaboration between schools, families, and community partners can create a holistic approach to student well-being. Community partnerships can provide various resources such as after-school programs, mental health clinics, and academic support services. These community resources can ensure that students receive the necessary support in all aspects of their lives, promoting academic achievement and psychological well-being (Reyes, 2024).

Theme 3. Student Well-Being and Support

Students faced unprecedented challenges in remote learning, including a lack of social interaction, increased stress levels, and difficulty staying motivated. As students return to in-person learning, it is essential to address their emotional needs and provide support for their mental health (Reyes, 2024).

The learner-centered approach of the English language teachers emerged as well during the interview. This approach adheres to the Bangsamoro Education Code of MBHTE (2021). The Education Code is learner-centered. It will establish a learner-centered education system with processes, inputs and standards designed to ensure the learners' well-being (MBHTE, 2021).

Participant One mentioned, *"We (English language teachers) learned new strategies for fostering communication and engagement both in virtual or in person as well as the importance of prioritizing student's social and emotional well-being."*

Participant Two elaborated her insights and said, *"As an English language teacher, my learning insights on the lingering effect of pandemic are knowing the abilities of my pupils, adjusting with them, and always discover new activities that will help to the learning of the pupils... My take-aways on these challenges is Education must not be taken for granted. Being able to teach and learn in school and in classrooms faced-to-faced is far better from the modules and online classes that we had during pandemic."*

Participant Nine learned and shared her insights on how to gain the interest of the learners who are not interested in schooling as it's first thing priority, *"To cope up with the less interest of learners in schooling, I make sure that my instructional materials are updated and suited to their interests."*

Theme 4. Continuous Learning and Improvement

The continuous learning and improvement were both significant for teachers and learners. One of the participants mentioned, *"Encountering the challenges and problems caused by lingering effect of the pandemic in education have provided insights into... investing and uplifting the professional development of educators."*

Participant Nine agreed on the continuous professional development of language teacher and said, *"Above-all, I should learn, relearn, and unlearn some trends in teaching so that I can provide the best teaching methods and strategies for my pupils."*

On the other hand, participant Ten mentioned the significant and crucial part of English language in Philippines and appreciated the learning process, *"As an English language teacher, I felt the urged need to teach the language accurately even after the pandemic. Little learning is good when it is continuous regardless of DepEd MELCs."*

As recommended in one of conducted researches, it is important to invest in social and emotional learning and training specifically addressed to teachers, both for improving teachers' emotional abilities and as a medium for improving class climate and students' emotional well-being (Geraci, Di Domenico & D'Amico, 2023).

Theme 5. Reflection and Growth

COVID-19 pandemic taught human kind such an unforgettable lessons and realizations in life. The post-pandemic era has provided numerous learning takeaways across different aspects of life, from healthcare to business and education. Several of the participants have reflection and can say that they've learned and have growth professionally.

Participant One shared, *"English Language teachers gained insight into the importance of flexible teaching methods... Overall, the pandemic has prompted reflection on various aspects of society, from how we work and learn how we prioritize health and well-being."*

Participant Three shared, *"With the lingering effects of the pandemic, it only showed us drastically how change and uncertainty remain as constants in the academe... Thus, many things might have changed especially on the learners and in the teaching and learning process, however, education still remains as one of the most essential things one needs to thrive in life."*

Participant Eight shared, *"Pandemic is just a challenge, it's up to you on how you face it... Just trust and have faith that all learners can read through your effort and parents' cooperation."*

Trust and Whalen (2020) remarked that pandemic has highlighted the need for continuous professional development and collaboration among language teachers. Sharing best practices and resources through online communities and professional networks has become more prevalent.

The learning insights of English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic.

The English language teacher-participants were asked to share their learning insights specifically the impact of the pandemic and its lingering effects as prevalent and continuous in their own context. Thematic analysis of their responses led to the formation of five themes for this second identifying question which is the impact made of the lingering effects of pandemic to language teachers.

Table 3.2. The learning insights (impact made) of English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Selected Quotations</i>
Adaptability and Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pandemic made me realize that learning will be meaningful with the guidance, expertise, and influence of the teacher emotionally. These situations give great impact on me as an English language teacher. I have to adjust my daily lesson plan and use objectives aligned to MELCS. The pandemic has been a transformative experience that has shaped me as an English teacher, reinforcing the importance of adaptability, flexibility, empathy, digital literacy,

Innovation and Creativity	<p>collaboration, and resilience in my professional practice.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This kind of situation made me a more competitive English Teacher to my pupils. It challenged me to go out from my comfort zone and find new things that will help my pupils to learn and love English subject. • As an English language teacher, I am challenged to explore new tools and strategies to keep pupils engaged and motivated. • I give more activities that correspond to the level of my pupils considering the struggling ones.
Human Connection and Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing beats learning from people like us who have real-life experiences and the ability to understand learners through our hearts. • Have empathy for your learners. Apply moral governance in Education to produce a brighter and better person someday. • I am trying to be friendlier in my approaches to lighten the burden. I see to it that our lesson is contextualized to what is known locally for pupils to relate themselves.
Continuous Learning and Professional Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As a teacher, I'll be more dedicated to my craft, discover things that help and benefit the learners, and attend seminars for my professional development. • We should always go back to the basic teaching strategies and focus on the value of human connection in education. • Education must continue from school to home. After listening and learning to teachers at school, learners should be taught again by their parents at home.
Quality Learning and Student-Centered Approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You can do anything that is best for your learners, not necessarily sticking to guidelines. Quality is the best, not the quantity. • Teachers can't be replaceable by technology alone and will never be when it comes to efficient and effective learning to happen. • We must value and appreciate each day more and do our best. Little by little at least, what you have taught to your learners will instill in them.

Theme 1. Adaptability and Flexibility

In educational context, the pandemic underscored the importance of flexibility in teaching methods. Language teachers have adapted to blended learning models, combining in-person and online instruction to cater to diverse learning needs (Macintyre, Gregersen & Mercer, 2020).

The English language teacher-participants shared some insights as impact of the lingering effect of pandemic as prevalent and continuous in in-person classes. Adaptability and flexibility emerged as theme out from participant's responses.

Participant Six shared, *"The pandemic made me an impact which made me realize that learning will be meaningful with the guidance, expertise and influence of the teacher emotionally."*

Participant Seven expressed, *"The pandemic has been a transformative experience that has shaped me as an English teacher, reinforcing the importance of adaptability, flexibility, empathy, digital literacy, collaboration and resilience in my professional practice."*

Participant Nine specified during the interview, *"These situations give great impact on me as an English language teacher. I have to adjust with my daily lesson plan, use objectives that is aligned to MELCs."*

All of the participants' statement and sentiments were all valid. Based on my experiences after the pandemic, during my session in my English class, I was so considerate with my pupils that I always checked them if they understood the lesson and if I need to translate in Filipino so that they could understand deeply the lesson. This scenario shows adaptability and flexibility of a language teachers.

The unpredictable nature of the pandemic necessitated a high degree of adaptability and flexibility in personal and professional contexts. Individuals and organizations alike had to quickly pivot and innovate to cope with changing circumstances (Spurk & Straub, 2020).

Theme 2. Innovation and Creativity

The participants shared that innovation and creativity should always be present to teachers' traits. It embodies the competitiveness and critical-thinking among teachers in conceptualizing and creating innovations or interventions.

The innovation and creativity were necessary to uplift the emphasis on students' engagement in blended learning. Maintaining student engagement in a virtual environment has been a significant challenge. Language teachers have learned to employ interactive activities, gamification, and multimedia resources to keep students motivated and engaged (Bao, 2020).

The above-findings were some of the innovative moves technologically by the language teachers. As shared by English language teachers from District VI:

Participant Two shared, *"This kind of situation made me became a more competitive English Teacher to my pupils. It challenged me*

to go out from my comfort zone and find new things that will help my pupils to learn and love English subject.”

Participant Four meant, *“As an English language teacher, the pandemic has great impact on me. I am challenged to explore new tools and strategies to keep pupils engaged and motivated...”*

Participant Five expressed, *“I give more activities that corresponds to level of my pupils considering the struggling ones.”*

As revealed by Donthu and Gustafsson (2020) that the pandemic accelerated digital transformation across various sectors, including education, healthcare, and commerce. Remote learning, telehealth services, and online shopping saw unprecedented growth, changing how people access services and interact with institutions.

The lingering effects of pandemic were not limited to educational sphere alone though we may say that the future’s nation manpower labor was affected its foundational skills in which may be have short or long-term impact.

Theme 3. Human Connection and Empathy

The participants realized the impact of crisis to human race. The human’s nature on emotional quotient prevailed even after pandemic as evident on the responses of the participants during the interview.

Participant Three stood firm and expressed, *“Nothing beats learning from people like us who have real-life experiences and ability to understand learner through our hearts.”*

Participant Five elaborated how empathy was being considered to the learners, *“I am trying to be friendlier in my approaches to lighten the burden. I teach using simple words, I explore ways for everyone to understand my talks such as giving examples, using into sentence or translate to first language. I see to it that our lesson is contextualized to what is known locally for pupils to relate themselves...”*

I agree with participant Eight who expressed that we should have empathy for our learners and should apply Moral Governance in Education to produce a brighter and better person someday.

Indeed, the pandemic’s impact to human connection have stimulated the sense of empathy and solidarity among the communities and stakeholders in society. This was affirmed on the study of Yunus, Mariyudi and Abubakar (2023) as they concluded that, in the face of a pandemic, government, teacher, and parent cooperation, as well as the ability to adapt to change, were the keys to the success of children’s education under any circumstance.

Theme 4. Continuous Learning and Professional Growth

As noted in the UNICEF’s report, *“Education in a Post-COVID World: Towards a RAPID Transformation”*, on the third domain of RAPID - the Prioritize Teaching Fundamentals, one of the recommended ways to implement the third domain was involving teachers in co-designing and facilitating curricular adjustments, and ensuring they are provided with training and guidance in implementing, adapting and prioritizing the curriculum (UNICEF, 2023).

Relatively, significant responses were noted during the interview on the commitment of English language teacher-participants on continuous learning and professional growth.

Participant Eight shared, *“As a teacher, I’ll be more dedicated to my craft. Discover things that help and benefit the learners. I need to attend seminars for my professional development.”*

On the other hand, participant Nine expressed that we should always go back to the basic teaching strategies and focus on the value of human connection in education. This is aligned as well to the statement of participant Six that education must continue from school to home. After listening and learning to teachers at school, learners should be taught again by their parents at home.

Based on experiences, the teachers have been attending training seminars either online or in-person and enrolling to postgraduate degrees which connote as pursuit for continuous learning and professional development.

Theme 5. Quality Learning and Student-Centered Approach

Education in all levels should always have quality learning outcomes and should always be learner-centered approach. In BARMM region, learner-centered approach was given emphasis in Bangsamoro Education Code (MBHTE, 2021).

When adhering to student-centered approach, considering the holistic well-being of the learners are necessary. As to agree with this, as mentioned on a blog post, one key strategy for supporting student well-being is to create a safe and inclusive learning environment. Encouraging open communication, providing emotional support, and fostering positive relationships between students and educators can go a long way in reducing anxiety and stress (Reyes, 2024).

The participants assured during the interview session with them that learners’ welfare and learning were the priority and should always be the priority of teachers, especially for English language teachers. It is due the fact of the aforementioned statement of participant Ten on the learning insights that English language is a crucial part of Philippines education. As evident, major subjects such as Mathematics, Science and English utilized English language as medium of instruction in its references and resources. Another cent,

Filipinos were non-native speaker of English. Despite of this scenario, as mentioned by the participants, they were adjusting their strategies or approaches in teaching English such as lowering the level of grade standard, translating the lesson from English to Filipino or sometimes to Mother-Tongue language just to ease the understanding of the learners on the lesson. These adjustments were manifestation of a learner-centered approach of education and being sustained even after the pandemic.

As shared by participant Six on the role of language teacher on effective learning, “... *Teachers can’t be replaceable by technology alone and will never be when it comes to efficient and effective learning to happen.*”

Furthermore, participant Ten stated that we must value and appreciate each day more and do our best. elaborated, “*You can do anything what is best for your learners and not necessarily sticking to guidelines... Little by little at least, what you have taught to your learners will instill in them. ... Quality is the best and not the quantity.*”

The realizations made on the lingering effects of pandemic.

The English language teacher-participants were asked to share their realization on the lingering effects of pandemic as prevalent and continuous on the learning of pupils after pandemic. Thematic analysis of their responses led to the formation of five themes for the third identifying question which talked about their realizations on the lingering effects of pandemic.

Table 3.3. *The realizations made on the lingering effects of pandemic*

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Selected Quotations</i>
Resilience and Dedication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The important realization I conclude is that as a teacher, I need to be flexible and resilient in delivering quality education to my learners. • The pandemic made me realize that our role as teachers is even more important these days...We should maximize the potential of our technology but it should never replace us. • The pandemic has been a transformative experience that has shaped me as an English teacher, reinforcing the importance of adaptability, flexibility, empathy, digital literacy, collaboration, and resilience in my professional practice.
Importance of Adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The effect of the pandemic highlighted the connectedness of our world and the importance of global cooperation in addressing crises. • The pandemic taught us our biggest lesson that nothing in this world is permanent...Brace yourself and prepare how to thrive in challenging times. • The pandemic has led me to profound realizations about the effects of crisis situation in education, prompting reflection, adaptation, and innovation.
Uncertainty and Preparedness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No one would ever think that there would be a pandemic that affected the entire world... Just go out of your comfort zone because not all the time you live in a comfortable life but most in an uncomfortable situation that needs you to be more appreciative and be ready for the next level of challenges in life. • As an English language teacher, I realized that nothing is really definite in Education. Even the competencies can be adjusted in times of necessities... Always look for ways that can be helpful to the learning of the pupils. • The pandemic thought me that we need to value life... Even in the worst situation, we can do it because we are already prepared for it.
Collaboration and Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the realization I pondered because of the lingering effect of the pandemic is that collaboration among teachers, parents, community stakeholders, and education partners are pivotal for the continuation of education despite all odds that hampers the learning continuity. • We are just passing by. In our littlest time, let's be grateful for the people around us, be appreciative of the beauty that surrounds us, and be faithful to the God above us. We must value and appreciate each day more, and do the best. • The pandemic was a tough era and its effects still affect us, especially our learners, until now but we can learn to navigate through these changes through our commitment and dedication to our learners.
Value of Physical Interaction in Teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I realized that teaching is not only delivering your lesson to your learners but to inculcate to them every single detail of your lesson and it is impossible to do it through modular or online teaching. • What is difficult today might be much difficult in the future...learning is better and easier when there is physical interaction with your teacher. • As a teacher, you take your lesson seriously and cooperate with your teacher because learning is better and easier when there is physical interaction with your teacher.

Theme 1. Resilience and Dedication

The resilience and dedication of English language teachers was portrayed by adapting to the crisis during pandemic and addressing its impact to education after pandemic.

As affirmation, Kim and Asbury (2020) remarked that during pandemic, the language teachers were managing their own stress while providing emotional support to students which became a key aspect to resilience.

The participants were asked to capsulized and shared their realizations on the lingering effect of pandemic. The resilience and dedication were the traits which have emerged as a common theme on their responses.

Participant Four expressed, *“The important realization I conclude is that as a teacher, I need to be flexible and resilient in delivering quality education to my learners. The pandemic gave us the sense to improve our learning in utilizing technology and to be adaptive in the changing way of teaching. Above all, indeed, teachers should be dynamic at all times.”*

The participants shared common statements on their realization about experiencing the transformative effect of pandemic to the educational system approaches that has shaped them as an English teacher and reinforced the importance of adaptability, flexibility, empathy, digital literacy, collaboration, and resilience in their professional practice.

Some of their statements were the following:

“As teacher, be optimistic and prepared. Always look for ways that can be helpful to the learning of the pupils,” participant One said.

“... But we can learn to navigate through these changes through our commitment and dedication to our learners,” participant Three said.

“The pandemic gave us the sense to improve our learning in utilizing technology and to be adaptive in the changing way of teaching. Above all, indeed, teachers should be dynamic at all times,” participant Four said.

“Some of realization I pondered because of the lingering effect of pandemic is that collaboration among teachers, parents, community stakeholders and education partners are pivotal for the continuation of education despite all odds that hampers the learning continuity. This collaboration is essential to make the learners future-ready and successful & productive citizen of our country,” participant Six said.

Both resiliency and dedication were pivotal for re-establishing and re-building the relationship of teachers and learners in post-pandemic educational context.

Theme 2. Importance of Adaptability

Stockwell and Wang (2023) remarked on their study that the future of post-pandemic language teaching will rest on the ability of teachers to create useful and appealing tasks, activities, and assessment that can be sustained in a two-dimensional, online context, at the same time, teachers need to nurture learners' emotional development. They suggested that adapting to post-pandemic language education settings needs to be something that takes place systematically and progressively to help teachers, learners, and educational institutions set challenging yet achievable goals in using technology as an integrated part of their language teaching and learning environments (Stockwell & Wang, 2023).

The significant of adaptability has been highlighted during the interviews to the participants. Participant One expressed, *“The effect of pandemic highlighted the connectedness of our world and the importance of Global cooperation in addressing crises.”*

Participant Five expressed also, *“The pandemic taught us our biggest lesson that nothing in this world is permanent... We are not in control, we never know what await us next. Brace yourself and prepare how to thrive in challenging times, explore opportunities, utilize your network and learn to better yourself.”*

Participant Seven shared, *“The pandemic has led me to profound realizations about the effects of crisis situation in education, prompting reflection, adaptation and innovation in the pursuit of resilient and equitable educational system.”*

Theme 3. Uncertainty and Preparedness

Indeed, life's turn and twist of points were unpredictable. One thing is for sure, uncertainty will be always there. Being prepared with any circumstance is an ace for the battle of uncertainties.

One of the recommendations by Hargreaves (2021) following from analysis of his study of how COVID-19 has impacted the professional capital of teachers and teaching and noted that education systems should be less bureaucratic and more agile in [their] ability to respond to crises, complexity and uncertainty such as natural disasters or sudden arrivals of large numbers of refugees, by moving as much decision-making power as possible to local districts, schools, and communities (Hargreaves, 2021). The language teachers realized this scenario and said the following statements during the interview:

“I realized that nothing is really definite in Education. Even the competences can be adjusted in times of necessities. And so, as teacher, be optimistic and prepared. Always look for ways that can be helpful to the learning of the pupils,” participant Two expressed.

“The pandemic thought me that we need to value life... Even in the worst situation, we can do it because we are already prepared for it,” participant Eight shared. As elaborated by participant Eight, *“No one would ever think that there would be a pandemic that affected*

the entire world. Just go out with your comfort zone because not all the time you live in a comfortable life but most in an uncomfortable situation that needs you to be more appreciative and be ready to the next level of challenges in life. With or without pandemic, we must always be ready.”

Theme 4. Collaboration and Support

The English language teachers valued the essence of collaboration and support as mentioned on their responses during the interview. Participant Three shared, “. *The pandemic was a tough era and its effects still affect us, especially our learners, until now but we can learn to navigate through these changes through our commitment and dedication to our learners.*”

Participant Five mentioned, “*We are just passing by. In our littlest time, let’s be grateful for the people around us, be appreciative of the beauty that surrounds us, and be faithful to the God above us. We must value and appreciate each day more, and do the best.*”

Participant Six expressed, “*Some of realization I pondered because of the lingering effect of pandemic is that collaboration among teachers, parents, community stakeholders and education partners are pivotal for the continuation of education despite all odds that hampers the learning continuity. This collaboration is essential to make the learners future-ready and successful & productive citizen of our country.*”

These sentiments were noted by Reyes (2024) on her blog post that collaboration between schools, families, and community partners can create a holistic approach to student well-being. Community partnerships can provide various resources such as after-school programs, mental health clinics, and academic support services. These community resources can ensure that students receive the necessary support in all aspects of their lives, promoting academic achievement and psychological well-being (Reyes, 2024).

Theme 5. Value of Physical Interaction in Teaching

Several of the participants highlighted the significant of physical interaction in teaching. As participant Ten elaborated, “*I realized that teaching is not only delivering your lesson to your learners but to inculcate to them every single details of your lesson and it is impossible to do it through modular or online teaching. I learned to put passion on my teaching because We cannot predict the future. What is difficult today might be much difficult in the future. When you are a student you take your lesson seriously and cooperate with your teacher because learning is better and easier when there is physical interaction with your teacher.*”

In a conducted study in Middle East, it revealed that physical interaction was identified as a very important aspect of pedagogic and deontic interactions in face-to-face classrooms (Al-Nofaie, 2023).

Thus, given the unpredictable scenario in future, it’s wise to invest in technological tools and resources for the online learning. Remote learning has already been practiced by other countries which have means to pursue online education. As time goes by, advance educational technological tools were discovered. Hence, physical interaction between teachers and learners is pivotal for holistic learning. Since English is a language and can be acquired, learned and applied effectively and efficiently in practical, interactive and meaningful context such as culture and norms, the human physical interaction is necessary as much as possible in learning English language.

As what social-constructivist believed, the language and culture are frameworks through which humans experience, communicate, and comprehend reality. According to Vygotsky, language and culture influence people’s intellectual growth and perception of their environment. Language transmission results in learning concepts being interpreted and assimilated through experience and cultural context (Deeba, Saleem & Kausar, 2021).

Conclusions

This qualitative study shows that the English language teachers lived experienced on the lingering effects of pandemic were adapting to changes in teaching-learning process, developing learners’ basic skills and comprehension, addressing the impact on learning progress and development, technology and connectivity insufficiency, recognizing the emotional toll response after the return of in-person classes and reflecting on professional teaching effectiveness. On the other hand, the experiences with the learning of pupils after pandemic were the dilemma on learning loss and academic gaps, lack of basic skills and comprehension, portraying emotional response and adjustment in returning to school and allocating efforts to bridge learning gaps and provide support to learners.

Based from the gathered data, the English language teachers’ challenges encountered were addressing learning loss and mental health, struggles in vocabulary comprehension, difficulty in teaching English and difficulty in adjusting to new learning environment. The interventions made were manifesting the adaptability and flexibility in teaching methods, establishing collaboration and community engagement, adapting teaching strategies, innovative teaching approaches, focus on student well-being, and adhering to continuous learning improvement.

Furthermore, the gained insights of English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic were embracing and valuing the essence of resiliency with adaptability, flexibility and dedication flexible teaching-learning process, acknowledging the significant contribution of collaboration with innovation and support, continuous learning and professional growth, adhering to student-centered approach and well-being and appreciating the human value and interactive connection with empathy in teaching-learning environment

of English class.

This qualitative study considers the implications of the lived experienced, challenges and learning insights of English language teachers on the lingering effects of pandemic on the following:

First, the Department of Education (DepEd), through the Information and Communications Technology Service (ICTS), mentioned the milestones of its Digital Rise Program during the 2022 World Book and Copyright Day Celebration (DepEd, 2022). The result of the study of the English language teachers adapting to changes in teaching-learning process with lack of technological resources and internet connection, may addressed with the intensification of implementing the Digital Rise Program of the department to embrace the digital technology for strengthening the adaptability and flexibility in learning. Adding to program's component should be the allocation and provision of adequate educational technology tools and means as to push by educational policy-makers and administrators.

Second, the result of the study may have implications on the next result of Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). One indicator of the country's state of basic education is the performance in the Program for International Student Assessment (Congressional Policy and Budget Research Department, 2024). Based on the 2022 PISA Result, the Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries globally in the student assessment conducted by the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) for 15-year-old learners. In the 2022 student assessment, the country scored approximately 120 points lower than the average scores, with scores of 355 in math, 347 in reading, and 373 in science (Ines, 2023). Addressing the learning loss and gaps through prioritizing the basic or fundamental skills of learners while accelerating the implementation and modernization of educational technology tools would result with better ranking for Philippines' performance in PISA.

Lastly, the result of the study would imply additional information to social science, medical and concerned stakeholder and education partners in field on conceptualizing programs and projects that would help on uplifting the mental health and well-being of both learners and teachers holistically to have quality and effective learning outcome in result.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

For English language teachers and school administrators, sustain the utilization of the available technological resources. Try to collaborate with other stakeholders and department to upgrade educational tools and to provide strong internet connection hub in areas with lack of connectivity like Department of Information, Communication and Technology (DICT). This is to reach out the last miles school and those learners who have lacked of means. Relatively, all of the teachers should capacitate themselves on the implementation of adaptive learning either online or in-person classes since uncertain circumstances are unpredictable.

On the basic skills of learners affected by learning loss and gaps, the department and MBHTE should intensify the reading program by allowing the teacher to focus more on teaching rather than involving on irrelevant and overlapping activities of the department. Also, the "no basic skills acquired, no promotion to higher grade" should be considered by the department as rule instead of "no retain" unwritten rule.

To the policymakers, department and regional administrators, strengthen the support on the mental health and well-being of both teachers and learners by providing necessary assistance and efficient compensation standards for teachers that will help them grow emotionally and professionally amidst of long-term lingering effects of pandemic economically and educationally.

To future researchers, they may conduct further studies about the result of the study and they may conduct this study on secondary English language teachers which may have comparative research method between elementary and secondary level.

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